

THE USAGE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS WHILE DEVELOPING READING SKILLS OF YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract. In this article, using interactive methods methods of developing reading ability of young students are discussed.

Key words: study, method, innovative technology, ability, development.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ ПРИ РАЗВИТИИ НАВЫКОВ ЧТЕНИЯ У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье с использованием интерактивных методов обсуждаются методы развития читательской способности младших школьников.

Ключевые слова: исследование, метод, инновационная технология, способность, развитие.

INTRODUCTION

There are two main approaches to teaching reading in English:

1. Look and say- teachers often use it as part of vocabulary teaching. So when children learn to say a new word they learn to read it. Using word cards (labeled on real objects or props) we can help children to recognize the word.
2. Phonics (letters used to make sounds) –sky, mask, skates. English spelling is difficult. It is better not to teach the names of letters when we starting to teach reading, as of course some of the letters of the English alphabet no longer match the actual sounds of the language. When we use phonics, we are teaching children the way the letter sounds, not the name of the letter.

Children can “read and do”, so we can give them short written instructions on cards to follow. They can understand the word through pictures, sounds or actions.

Tips for teaching reading:

- focus on meaning;
- word recognition;
- prediction;
- making the connection between familiar sounds and written words or phrases;
- Meaning is the most important element in reading

Always remember just as listening comes before speaking, so reading comes before writing.

READING TASK

The name of the activity: “Which group’s sun is brighter?”

Time required: 15 minutes

Equipments : overhead projector , Power Point slides

Materials :Two big circles , sunrays, coloured pencils or markers, sheets of paper , pictures of symbols, handout for guessing the title of the lesson, a poster , pupils’ worksheet , instruction for teachers

Interaction : individual , group work and plenary

Objectives:

- a) educational : to enable PP to talk about their family members and to practice the usage of the construction “This is ...”;
- b) developing: to give them an opportunity to choose the best symbol for their mothers and improve their intensive reading , listening and speaking skills.

Outcomes:

By the end of the lesson pupils will:

- be able to talk about their family members and to practice the usage of the construction “This is ...”;
- have an opportunity to choose a symbol for their mothers and improve their intensive reading, listening and speaking skills.

At the beginning of the lesson teacher will show a handout with different pictures. Pupils should think logically and guess what word is hidden there. In this way they can find out the name of the lesson.

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PRE-READING ACTIVITY

Teacher will pre-teach new words (This is , family , mother, father , sister, brother, hand in hand) using fingers of the hand. Explain them that:

The thumb is for “Father”

The index finger is for “Mother”

The ring finger is for “Sister”

The little finger is for “Brother”

Teacher wears a glove in her left hand , draws faces and then showing each finger introduces family members. If we present new words with action pupils can memorize them more quickly.

WHILE – READING ACTIVITY

Teacher will present the poem “My family” using rebus pictures. Rebus pictures will help them to memorize the names of family members. Unfamiliar words are shown by pictures and it will be easy for young learners to understand the meaning of the new word. This is my

This is my

This is my

This is my

Mother , Father
Sister , Brother

With one another

POST - READING ACTIVITY

To consolidate the names of family members and the construction “This is ” teacher will organize and play an activity “Which groups’ sun is brighter?”.

Instructions:

1. Divide the class into two groups by coloured geometrical shapes.
2. Give a sunray() for each member of the group. That means that each pupil is stand for one word. There are eight sunrays .
3. Tell them that they should put the sunrays (words) in order and form the sun (a sentence).
4. If they put a sunray (picture describing a word) in a wrong place, they will lose a sunray (a point).
5. The group which has more sunrays will become the winner and their SUN will shine brightly .

Procedure:

Teacher sticks two big circles on the blackboard. Members of each group comes to the blackboard and sticks the first sunray (This); If any member sticks another word the group will lose a point. And in this way pupils one by one (is, my, mother. This , is , my , father) should stick the sunrays and form the shape of the sun. The group which has more sunrays will become the winner and their SUN will shine brightly.

Playing this activity pupils will be able to improve their intensive reading , speaking and listening skills. These activity is useful for all kinds of learners: visual , auditory, tactile and kinaesthetic.

This activity is suitable for young learners and good for pupils of the primary and secondary (5th -6th forms) education level.

We created this activity according to our work experience. We hope that the learners will be interested in this activity and like it very much and ask to play it again. This activity can be organized for practising the vocabulary and grammar rules of nearly all units and it will be very

effective because PP will be able to memorize words and rules through reading the poem (with rebus pictures) and playing the game .

If this activity does not work well we can offer another one.

The name of the activity is “Symbols” . We know that all pupils like drawing. That’s why we can organize a game for improving their reading and drawing skills.

Step 1: Distribute circles like the head of a woman. Pupils should draw eyes, a nose and a mouth of their mothers.

CONCLUSION

According to their drawing we can find out about characteristic features of their mothers. If they draw a happy face , it means they love their mothers.

Step 2: Then teacher presents a handout with different pictures (the sun , the moon and stars, a flower and a rainbow). Pupils should choose a symbol for their mothers and explain the reason. (If this task is difficult for them they can use L1 to express their ideas).

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